

Additional file 1. Results of multiple linear regression models without control for confounding variables

	NHS vs. SMC	NHS vs. MCI	NHS vs. AD	AD vs. SMC	AD vs. MCI	MCI vs. SMC
IL-1 α	0.1 (-0.40 to 0.42) <i>p</i> =0.96	-0.13 (-0.56 to 0.3) <i>p</i> =0.54	3.29 (-0.29 to 6.61) <i>p</i> =0.052	3.28 (-0.84 to 7.41) <i>p</i> =0.12	3.42 (-1.38 to 8.23) <i>p</i> =0.16	-0.14 (-0.53 to 0.24) <i>p</i> =0.46
IL-1 β	-0.35 (-1.2 to 0.54) <i>p</i> =0.44	-0.28 (-1.29 to 0.72) <i>p</i> =0.57	2.6 (-0.21 to 5.51) <i>p</i> =0.07	3.0 (-0.43 to 6.43) <i>p</i> =0.86	2.9 (-1.06 to 6.93) <i>p</i> =0.14	0.06 (-0.49 to 0.62) <i>p</i> =0.81
IL-1Ra	-23.1 (-47.5 to 1.2) <i>p</i> =0.06	14.8 (-13.1 to 42.9) <i>p</i> =0.29	58.1 (3.8 to 112.4) <i>p</i> =0.036	81.3 (16.5 to 146.1) <i>p</i> =0.014	43.2 (-32.1 to 118.6) <i>p</i> =0.26	38.0 (11.2 to 64.8) <i>p</i> =0.006
IL-18	-46.6 (-74.5 to -18.6) <i>p</i> =0.001	19.1 (-19.3 to 57.6) <i>p</i> =0.32	64.2 (-6.1 to 134.6) <i>p</i> =0.073	110.8 (26.8 to 194.8) <i>p</i> =0.010	45.02 (-56.3 to 146.7) <i>p</i> =0.38	65.8 (27.6 to 103.9) <i>p</i> =0.001
IL-33	-0.45 (-1.05 to 0.15) <i>p</i> =0.14	-0.25 (-0.93 to 0.43) <i>p</i> =0.46	2.6 (0.29 to 5.0) <i>p</i> =0.028	3.1 (0.23 to 5.9) <i>p</i> =0.034	2.9 (-0.43 to 6.2) <i>p</i> =0.088	0.19 (-0.19 to 0.58) <i>p</i> =0.31
sIL-1R1	-218.9 (-291.5 to -146.2) <i>p</i> <0.001	-56.6 (-161.06 to 47.7) <i>p</i> =0.28	407.8 (312.9 to 502.86) <i>p</i> <0.001	626.8 (519.5 to 734.04) <i>p</i> <0.001	464.52 (317.6 to 611.3) <i>p</i> <0.001	162.2 (45.74 to 278.8) <i>p</i> =0.007
sIL-1R2	-961.1 (-1516.8 to -405) <i>p</i> =0.001	3570.6 (2777.3 to 4363.8) <i>p</i> <0.001	-112.0 (-743.8 to 519.6) <i>p</i> <0.726	849.0 (306.7 to 1391.2) <i>p</i> =0.002	-3682.6 (-4538.2 to -2827) <i>p</i> <0.001	4531.7 (3795.0 to 5268.3) <i>p</i> <0.001
sIL-1R3	1273.1 (570.6 to 1975.6) <i>p</i> <0.001	-178.7 (-936.0 to 578.6) <i>p</i> <0.64	2762.5 (2042.4 to 3482.7) <i>p</i> <0.001	1489.4 (688.8 to 2290.0) <i>p</i> <0.001	2941.2 (2093.1 to 3789.3) <i>p</i> <0.001	-1451.8 (-2271.4 to -631.9) <i>p</i> =0.001
sIL-1R4	-648.3 (-1550.9 to 254.2) <i>p</i> =0.158	-471.9 (-1501.8 to 557.9) <i>p</i> =0.336	5623.9 (4081.6 to 7166.3) <i>p</i> <0.001	6272.3 (4396.3 to 8148.3) <i>p</i> <0.001	6095.8 (3922.5 to 8269.1) <i>p</i> <0.001	176.4 (-1013.2 to 1366.1) <i>p</i> =0.76
IL-18BP	-4659 (-5579 to -3539.6) <i>p</i> <0.001	-4722.2 (-6011 to -3342.9) <i>p</i> <0.001	8092.7 (6254 to 9931) <i>p</i> <0.001	12752.3 (10748.5 to 14756) <i>p</i> <0.001	12815 (10490.1 to 15139) <i>p</i> <0.001	-62.6 (-1027.6 to 902.2) <i>p</i> =0.89
free IL-18	13.18 (-1.55 to 27.92) <i>p</i> =0.79	50.51 (32.43 to 68.6) <i>p</i> <0.001	-15.60 (-43.27 to 11.98) <i>p</i> =0.26	-28.8 (-62.2 to 4.57) <i>p</i> =0.09	-66.16 (-105.8 to -26.5) <i>p</i> =0.001	37.33 (16.93 to 57.7) <i>p</i> <0.001

Values are β coefficients (95% confidence intervals) and *p* values.

AD, Alzheimer's disease; MCI, mild cognitive impairment; NHS, normal healthy subjects; SMC, subjective memory complaint.